

Determination of Bifenthrin Residues on the Eggplant's Soil, Leaf and Fruits

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Abstract:

The determination of Bifenthrin residues considered one of the most significant aspect, especially in the environmental pollution. The estimation of Bifenthrin residues in leaves, soil, and the eggplant fruits revealed that the residues can be decreased faster in the soil and the fruits compared to the leaves. The dissipation period in terms of soil and fruits was 7 days, while in the case of the leaves was 10 days for the both concentrations 1 and 1.5 mL L⁻¹. As the results also confirmed that the dissipation of Bifenthrin residues are subjected to the first-order kinetic reaction. All residues demonstrated that the rates of dissipation almost resemble for both used concentrations. In

the soil, leaves, and fruits for 1 and 1.5 mL L⁻¹ were 0.303, 0.403, 0.374, 0.380, 0.469, and 0.463 day⁻¹ respectively. As this kinetic reaction conducted to the half-life of Bifenthrin residues on leaves, soil, and fruits for both concentrations as following: 1.8, 1.8, 2.2, 1.7, 1.4, and 1.4 days respectively. The study also showed the lack of importance of food processes in reducing Bifenthrin residues, suggesting that the consumption of the eggplant depends on the safety removing Bifenthrin residues compared to conducting food operations.

Keywords: *Tetranychus urticae*, greenhouses, Bifenthrin, GC-MS.

Introduction

Tetranychus urticae, the two-spotted spider mite is considered a key pest of Cucurbitaceae and Solanaceae, for example eggplants, tomatoes, cucumbers, peppers, zucchini, especially in greenhouse crops (Jeppson *et al.* 1975). This mite feeds on plant cells by sucking their contents, causing leaf yellowing, then drop the leaf and

finally plant death (Helle and Sabelis 1985). In Iraq, the spreading of vegetables that planted in a greenhouse in the year 2006 approximately 23,665 hectares. While their production scored was decreased into 51.7 tones. This decline might be because of the methods used and also the lack of the suitable service process (AL-Taey *et al.* 2017). Multiple studies have been performed to control the two-spotted spider in

the field. For example, the study that carried out by Tulail and Mohammadali (2021) evaluated a number of various pesticides against *Tetranychus urticae* for example, Vapcomic 1.8 % EC and Transact 1.8 EC by applying two different concentrations of 0.5 and 1.0 mL L⁻¹. They found that Both Transact and Vapcomic significantly affected the mortality of *Tetranychus urticae*. In addition, they estimated the residue levels in cucumber fruit. They found that the residues dissipated after 7 days of application.

Bifenthrin is a synthetic insecticide which belonging to the pyrethrins group. It works through their impact on targets voltage-gated sodium channels and also neurotoxic effect (Riar 2014). Hanafi *et al.* (2016) evaluated a group of pesticide, including Bifenthrin under open field on peas. As Mokhtari and Mouhouche (2016) estimated the residues of Bifenthrin in strawberry and tomato in Algeria. Despite some pesticides like Bifenthrin is considered not dangerous against people, but, the excessive and extremely use it leaves their residues with various levels in soil, plant leaf, and fruit, resulting in deleterious effect on the consumers. Therefore, the current study was performed to determine the Bifenthrin residues in soil, fruits, and plant leaves. Additionally, to find out the importance treating of food to access the best decision in order to protect consumers from the harm impact of the pollution.

Material and Methods

The Spraying of Pesticide

This study was carried out at one of the greenhouses of the College of Agriculture-University of Karbala in Al-Hussainiya District -Karbala Governorate to conduct an experiment on the eggplant crop. The area of the greenhouse was 18 x 5 m², the soil was prepared, the streams were opened, drip irrigation technology was used to water the plants, and the house was covered with polyethylene nylon. Barcelona eggplant seeds were used. The seeds were sown in cork dishes on 1/8/2019, and the seedlings were transferred to the greenhouse on 15/9/2019. The planting was in four lines (murouz) and the

distance between one plant and another was 45 cm. And applied all the agricultural practices were applied for example, plowing, cleaning and removing the weeds. Eggplant plants were treated on 15/11/2019, approximately two months after transplanting the seedlings. Divide the greenhouse into two halves by leaving a space between them to prevent interference between the concentrations used. Three replicates were used, and in each replicate a categorical division was divided into four treatments, three of them for the pesticide and one for comparison (without pesticide). To treat plants with pesticide, a small 5 liter sprayer was used to avoid interference between the two concentrations of pesticide in other treatments and to control the target plant and its parts. Two concentrations (1 and 1.5 mL L⁻¹) were applied to control the mites on the eggplant at the greenhouse. Bifenthrin (Talstar 10 EC) were applied to control on the *T. urticae*.

Extraction and Determination of Bifenthrin Residues

Bifenthrin residues were extracted by following the protocol of (Dong *et al.*, 2009). While its residues calculated in the Ministry of Science and Technology is using gas chromatography mass spectrophotometry (GCMS QP2010 Ultra SHIMADZU). The GCMS's conditions were demonstrated in the (Table 1).

Table 1. The Conditions of GCMS Analysis

[AOC-20i+s]	:1
# of Rinses with Pre solvent	
# of Rinses with Solvent(post)	:2
# of Rinses with Sample	:1
Plunger Speed(Suction)	:High
Viscosity Comp. Time	:0.2 sec
Plunger Speed(Injection)	:High
Syringe Insertion Speed	:High
Injection Mode	:Normal
Pumping Times	:5
Inj. Port Dwell Time	:0.3 sec

Terminal Air Gap	:No	
Plunger Washing Speed	:High	
Washing Volume	:8uL	
Syringe Suction Position	:0.0 mm	
Syringe Injection Position	:0.0 mm	
Solvent Selection	:All A,B,C	
[GC-2010]		
Column Oven Temp.	:50.0 °C	Hold Time(mi n)
Injection Temp.	:280.00 °C	
Injection Mode	:Split	
Flow Control	:Linear Velocity	
Pressure Mode	:100.0 kPa	
Total Flow	:55.4 mL/min	
Column Flow	:1.69 mL/min	
Linear Velocity	:47.2 cm/sec	
Purge Flow	:3.0 mL/min	
Split Ratio	:30.0	
High Pressure	:OFF	
Injection Carrier Gas Saver	:OFF	
Splitter Hold	:OFF	
Oven Program	Temperature(°C)	
Rate		
-	50.0	1.00
20.00	120.0	1.00
10.00	300.0	3.00

Statistical analysis

Data on Bifenthrin residues was evaluated by applying the first-order kinetic reaction. Where the slope represented the rate of residue dissipation (K a day). While the half-life of the residues was calculated according to the First-order reaction.

Results

Dissipation of Bifenthrin Residues on the Eggplant Leaves, Soil, and the Fruits

Figure (1-A) shows the Bifenthrin residual dissipated over a time (days). These residues resulted from using two different concentrations, which were 1 and 1.5 mL of Bifenthrin. Those residues declined from (985.3 to 22.35) ppm and from (1011.2 to 21.45) ppm for both concentrations 1 and 1.5 mL respectively. As Figure (1-B) revealed that the dissipation rate at 1 and 1.5 mL L^{-1} are approximately closed. It scored 0.37 day^{-1} and 0.38 day^{-1} respectively. This leading to the half-life of Bifenthrin residues on the eggplant leaves were 1.83 and 1.82 day^{-1} respectively for both concentrations.

Figure 1. (A): Dissipation of Bifenthrin Residues on the Eggplant Leaves, and (B): Kinetic Dissipation of Bifenthrin Based on the First-Order Reaction

However, Figure (2-A) demonstrated the decreasing of Bifenthrin residues from the soil. It clearly sees that residues decreased from (855.25 to 43.2) ppm at the concentration of 1 mL L^{-1} , whilst the residues dropped from (802 to

50.35) ppm when 1.5 mL L^{-1} was applied. The kinetic measurements of the residues decreasing can be confirmed by calculating the rate of residue dissipation for both the used concentrations. The rate of dissipation in the

case of 1 and 1.5 mL L⁻¹ was 0.303 and 0.403 day⁻¹ (Figure 2-B) respectively. Moreover, the half-life recorded 2.2 and 1.7 day respectively. It is

noted that the dissipation of residues of both the used concentration were almost similar.

Figure 2. (A): Dissipation of Bifenthrin Residue in the Soil, and (B): Kinetic Dissipation of Bifenthrin Based on the First-Order Reaction

On the other hand, the Bifenthrin residues on the eggplant fruits suffer from the degradation. Figure (3-A) elucidates the diminishing of Bifenthrin residues from (943.15 to 41.2) and from (965.2 to 44.95) ppm for the 1 and 1.5 mL L⁻¹ respectively. While the data, kinetic

evaluation of the two used concentrations illustrated that the dissipation rate for both concentrations are quite resemble. It was 0.469 and 0.463 day⁻¹ respectively. According to that, the half-life of dissipation period are 1.4 day⁻¹ for both concentrations.

Figure 3. (A): Dissipation of Bifenthrin Residue in the Eggplant Fruits, and (B): Kinetic Dissipation of Bifenthrin Based on the First-Order Reaction

On the other side, Figure (4) shows the role of food processes in reducing of the Bifenthrin residues. From the data of the figure below can be seen that the normal water contributed in reducing Bifenthrin residues from (300.2 to 295.4) ppm, soap and water (123.1 to 120.0) ppm, saline water 100 g L, (53.4 to 50.1) ppm,

sodium bicarbonate (110.4 to 105.1) ppm, potassium permanganate (133.5 to 130.2) ppm, saline water 50 g L⁻¹ (95.5 to 94.1) ppm, acetic acid (92.1 to 90.1) ppm, and peeling process (33.4 to 31.2) ppm.

Figure 4. The Role of Food Process in the Removing of Bifenthrin Residues

Discussion

Results showed that the Bifenthrin residual dissipated over a time (days). The rapid degradation of these residues belongs to various reasons. The most important is the environmental factors. Such as, the sunlight, temperature, and air, where those factors contribute to fast degradation of most pesticides. However, the kinetic evaluation of Bifenthrin residue dissipation undergoes the first-order kinetic reaction. As Figure (1-B) revealed that the dissipation rate at 1 and 1.5 mL L⁻¹ are approximately closed. It scored 0.37 day⁻¹ and 0.38 day⁻¹ respectively. This leading to the half-life of Bifenthrin residues on the eggplant leaves were 1.83 and 1.82 day⁻¹ respectively for both concentrations.

It is clear that the decreasing of Bifenthrin residues from the soil. It is noted that the dissipation of residues of both the used concentration were almost similar. This can be seen by comparing between the rate of dissipation for both the concentrations, which also had almost identical. The majority of pesticides can quickly degrade in the soil due to the presence of many microorganisms like bacteria, fungi, and protozoa. These microbes can utilise from the pesticides as a carbon source in their metabolisms. A study of Sharma and

Singh (2012) found that the half-life was 147 and 330 days depends on the presence and absence of the soil microorganisms respectively. On the other hand, the Bifenthrin residues on the eggplant fruits suffer from the degradation. Typically, the dissipation of the residues might be direct exposure of Bifenthrin residues to sunlight, in addition the large surface of the eggplant, leading to the fast degradation of Bifenthrin residues due to the sunlight, the length of sunlight period, and winds. These abiotic factors are considered the key role of the residue degradation. The rapid losing of residues is significantly interesting outcome. Because this encourages the harvest of the eggplant fruits after the spraying the Bifenthrin approximately one week. Where these residues reached into negligible value (not detect) at the tenth day of the application. Accordingly, this acaricide can be used before the eggplant harvest, furthermore, it has proficiently role in the controlling of the mite *T. urticae* during the eggplant's plantation season. In the conducted study previously, Bifenthrin residues were determined by using gas chromatography equipped the electron capture detector in the eggplant and the soil under opened field condition. This study showed that Bifenthrin residues have various half-lives on the fruits and soil, it was 17.8 to 25.7 days in soil, and 3.3 to 4.1 days in eggplant (Shi et al., 2016). In addition, the results give an indicator regarding health security of consumers. Because the residues of Bifenthrin did not exceed the maximum residue levels on the eggplant. Alike, our results also confirm this conclusion. Results also explained the role of food processes in reducing of the Bifenthrin residues. This contribution did not be effective where these processes slightly contributed in decreasing of Bifenthrin residues. Therefore, the using of all these processes does not have a significant role in losing of the Bifenthrin residues from the eggplant fruits. But the most important aspect is waiting the safety period, which equals between 1 to 2 days. In this case, abiotic factors play a crucial operation in declining the Bifenthrin residues compared to the food processes. Despite Al-Maksousi (2021) revealed that the necessary role of various food process in decreasing of abamectin residues

from cucumber fruits from 343.1 mg kg⁻¹ into 131.8 mg kg⁻¹ after three days of the treatments, the current study showed there is no crucial role of the washing process in decreasing the bifenthrin residues by the various process.

Conclusions

To sum up the results, it demonstrated that Bifenthrin residues can be faster degraded from the leaves, soil, and fruits. This is because many environmental factors. For example, the wind, temperature, air, sunlight, and its period during a day, especially in Iraq, where the density and length of sunlight are a crucial factor. Moreover, the determination of these residues recorded the dramatically reducing whether in leaves, soil or fruits owing to the harsh climate in Iraq, in particularly during the summer. This suggests to the ability to harvest the fruits after one week of Bifenthrin application. Furthermore, the kinetic reaction of residues was evaluated by applying the first-order kinetic reaction. This evaluation confirmed the faster the degradation of Bifenthrin reducing in all studied part.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors of the current investigation would like to declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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